

Sustainable Weed Management in Agriculture with Laser-Based Autonomous Tools

Enabling navigation for autonomous robots in early-stage crop growth

J. Herrera, L. Emmi, P. González-de-Santos.

World FIRA, Toulouse
December 8th, 2021

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

Enabling navigation for autonomous robots in early-stage crop growth

J. Herrera, P. González-de-Santos, L. Emmi

Centre for Automation and Robotics (CAR), UPM-CSIC, 28500 Arganda del Rey, Madrid, Spain

In the last decades, autonomous vehicles for agricultural applications are drawing the attention of farmers to carry sensors and implements throughout the working field. Thus, the activity for developing robust, safe and eco-friendly autonomous vehicles has increased significantly. However, agricultural fields are unstructured, changeable and diverse environments, where weather conditions, luminosity, different stages of crop growth, among others, make the navigation problem a challenge for autonomous robotic systems.

Conventional localization and perception systems for autonomous navigation such as GNSS, 2D and 3D LIDAR, stereo cameras, among others, as well as new methodologies based on artificial intelligence (AI) are not enough to develop by themselves a robust system capable of fully autonomous navigation in these harsh environments. Precise mapping, setting-up the working area, correction signal failure, and GNSS-denied zones are some of the major challenges in autonomous navigation.

Among the possible applications of autonomous robots in agricultural environments is the elimination of weeds using selective methods such as high-power laser. These treatments normally occur when crops are in their early stages of growth. Throughout the literature, there are many researches on autonomous navigation in agricultural environments based on crop row guidance, but these studies solve the problem when the crop is already in a mature growth stage or in crop types with an appropriate morphology for LIDAR based methods, such as vineyards. Early growth stage of plants, together with the unevenness in ground height and the presence of weeds make conventional perception systems unable to identify the crop properly, and thus preventing its further use for autonomous row-guidance.

This work presents an approach for developing smart perception systems to enable autonomous robots to safely navigate in fields in an early stage of crop growth without relying on absolute location systems, such as GNSS. The final system will be able to generically identify and classify diverse wide-row crops, eliminating the outliers, in order to estimate the crop lines for later navigation.

The first step for the development of this smart perception system is the correct characterization of the field. A model based on deep learning techniques that is able to detect early stage crops has been developed. The tests were carried out using a manually operated mobile platform, equipped with an RGB and a ToF (time of flight) cameras. Image acquisition was done on an experimental field during different time periods, located at the Centre for Automation and Robotics. The target crops were corn and sugar beet. Moreover, this work also demonstrates the capabilities of integrating crop detection into already trained models that are capable of detecting other types of objects, such as mobile and fixed obstacles commonly found in a crop field. The results show how the system is able to detect the plants and obstacles properly, thus enabling the future development of the final navigation system.

Site-specific weed management

Chemical

Mechanical

Thermal

High-power laser

Navigation on the field

- Unstructured, changeable and diverse environment
- Weather conditions, luminosity
- Different stages of crop growth (Early stage)
- Unevenness in ground height
- Presence of weeds

- GNSS

Perception systems:

- LIDAR
- RGB cameras
- Time of flight camera (ToF)

Crop identification

Wide-row crops

Narrow-row crops

Object detection

RGB

ToF

Labeling

N=50

Labeling

N=50

Training of Deep Neural Networks

Inference:

Segmentation

Matching with ToF point cloud

Filtering

Clustering

Lines extraction

Line following

RGB segmentation

Segmentation
mAP 80%

SegNet
U-Net
MobileNets

ToF intensity image

Segmentation

Matching with ToF point cloud

Filtering

Clustering

Lines extraction

Line following

ToF point cloud

ToF point cloud

Top view

Lateral view

Ground plane estimation and filtering

Lateral view

Point cloud filtered and segmented

Top view

Lateral view

Wheat point cloud

Top view

Lateral view

Clustering

DBSCAN

RANSAC: line fitting

Line following

RGB object detection

Object detection

YOLOv4

Test case: Wide-row crops

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

ANY QUESTIONS?

This work is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000256".